
Learning Hyperparameter Schedules with Meta Population Based Training

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Abstract

Choosing optimal hyperparameters in reinforcement learning can greatly impact both the final performance and sample efficiency of an agent, as demonstrated by numerous studies on this subject in this area. Classical, static methods that seek a favorable hyperparameter configuration before training starts, aiming to keep this configuration fixed throughout the run have been traditionally employed to tackle this problem. However, adapting hyperparameters dynamically according to the training profile can often yield better results. This insight led to the field of Dynamic Algorithm Configuration (DAC). In this work, we investigate whether dynamic tuning of hyperparameters in reinforcement learning can be further improved by incorporating meta-data from related tasks. Learning hyperparameter schedules involves modeling non-stationary, complex functions. To address this challenge, we employ a deep kernel Gaussian Process, which allows us to capture intricate patterns in the hyperparameter space to guide the dynamic tuning of a parallel population of agents. In addition, we "stress-test" this approach by examining the influence of meta-data volume and the distribution of related tasks on performance. Our findings indicate that, under certain conditions, meta-learning can significantly accelerate convergence. When tasks are sufficiently related, the approach yields meaningful speedups compared to PB2, whereas when the meta-tasks are highly dissimilar, the benefits of the meta data diminish although our approach still outperforms the default static hyperparameter configurations. Furthermore, our method explores the hyperparameter space in ways that differ from PB2, highlighting a unique exploratory behavior that could offer further insights into efficient hyperparameter tuning for reinforcement learning tasks.

1 Introduction

Hyperparameter optimization is a critical component of reinforcement learning, with optimal hyperparameters often varying across tasks and over the course of training. Traditional static approaches, which tune hyperparameters before training begins, have shown some performance gains, but yet do not explicitly respond to the dynamic, non-stationary nature of the problem. Dynamic Algorithm Configuration (DAC) [Adriaensen et al., 2022] methods, such as Population-Based Bandits (PB2) [Parker-Holder et al., 2020], address this challenge by learning dynamic hyperparameter schedules during training. PB2 leverages a Gaussian Process with a time-varying kernel trained on data from the current agents that are training to adapt hyperparameters for a population of agents, offering improved adaptability over static approaches. The high performance it has shown is attributed to the strong and continuous information signal it gets from the agents training. It has shown improvements in comparison to its predecessor PBT, which explored the search space in an uninformed manner by applying perturbations to the hyperparameters [Jaderberg et al., 2017], as well as other baselines such as random search [Bergstra and Bengio, 2012], Bayesian optimization [Brochu et al., 2010], and asynchronous successive halving (ASHA) [Li et al., 2018].

In this work, we propose an approach that enhances population-based methods by incorporating deep kernel learning and meta-data to learn hyperparameter schedules, focusing on reinforcement learning settings. At the core of our method is a deep kernel, trained on incoming data from the current trials and hyperparameter schedule data from other related tasks, providing a flexible model for guiding hyperparameter adaptation. By combining the strengths of meta-learning and population-based approaches, our method aims to dynamically adjust hyperparameters in a way that is robust to varying levels of task similarity and data availability.

This problem is challenging because reinforcement learning environments can vary widely, making it non-trivial to generalize from one environment to another. Additionally, effectively incorporating meta-data while avoiding negative transfer (i.e., when unrelated meta-data degrades performance) is a key difficulty.

1.1 Contributions

To address these challenges, our contributions are as follows:

- **Deep Kernel Learning with Meta-Data:** We incorporate meta-data from related tasks to train a deep kernel that guides hyperparameter scheduling, improving generalization across environments.
- **Performance Robustness:** We show that our approach is robust to variations in data sampling distribution and availability.
- **Controlled Exploration in Hyperparameter Space:** Our scheduler explores the search space in a more controlled manner than PB2, smoothly transitioning between configurations instead of swinging between extremes.

We conduct our experiments using the CARL library [Benjamins et al., 2022]. We select the Cart Pole and Lunar Lander environments [Brockman, 2016]

2 Problem Statement

Dynamic hyperparameter optimization in reinforcement learning requires adapting hyperparameters θ_t over time t to maximize an agent’s performance efficiently. This problem involves balancing exploration and exploitation in a high-dimensional, dynamic, and non-stationary hyperparameter space.

The surrogate model $g(\Delta\tilde{r}; \mathcal{D})$ predicts the **change** $\Delta\tilde{r}$ in reward. The dataset \mathcal{D} , used to train g , combines:

- **Current Trial Data:** $\mathcal{D}_{current} = \{(\theta, t, \tilde{r}, \Delta\tilde{r})\}$, collected during optimization.
- **Meta-Data from Related Tasks:** $\mathcal{D}_{meta} = \{(\theta, t, \tilde{r}, \Delta\tilde{r}, c)\}$, gathered from related tasks, we also concatenate an environment identifier c .

Thus, $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D}_{current} \cup \mathcal{D}_{meta}$.

The surrogate model g employs a Deep Spectral Mixture (SM) Kernel [Wilson et al., 2016], combining the flexibility of spectral mixture kernels with the representational power of neural networks. Input features x (hyperparameters θ , time indices t , task-specific features c , reward r) are mapped into a latent space $z = h_\phi(x)$ via a feed forward neural network h_ϕ . The kernel in this latent space is defined as:

$$k_{SM}(z, z') = \sum_{q=1}^3 w_q \exp(-2\pi^2(z - z')^\top \Lambda_q (z - z')) \cos(2\pi\mu_q^\top (z - z')),$$

where Λ_q , μ_q , and w_q are learned parameters of the kernel.

3 Methodology

Our method combines population-based training, deep kernel learning, and meta-data to adaptively schedule hyperparameters for reinforcement learning agents. The training process is outlined in

Algorithm 1. During training, surrogate model g is optimized with early stopping to prevent overfitting. The training data is split into 80% for training and 20% for validation. Hyperparameter updates are guided by Bayesian Optimization with the Upper Confidence Bound (UCB) acquisition function:

$$\alpha(\theta) = \mu_g(\theta) + \kappa \cdot \hat{\sigma}_r(\theta),$$

where μ_g is the mean predicted by the surrogate model, and κ controls exploration. Variance predictions from our kernel are replaced with those from a secondary Gaussian Process r with an RBF kernel, which provides more reliable uncertainty estimates ($\hat{\sigma}_r$). Finally, To enable efficient parallel training, batch optimization is performed, generating multiple hyperparameter suggestions at each perturbation interval. This allows simultaneous exploration-exploitation trade-offs across agents following Desautels et al. [2014].

Algorithm 1 Meta Deep Kernel Learning (Meta-DKL)

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0: Initialize  $N$  agents with random hyperparameters  $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N$ .
0: while training steps  $\leq$  max steps do
0:   Train agents for the current interval and collect data  $\mathcal{D}_{current}$ .
0:   Update  $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \mathcal{D} \cup \mathcal{D}_{current}$ .
0:   Train the deep kernel  $g(\cdot; \mathcal{D})$  on collected data and meta data.
0:   for each poorly performing agent  $i$  in lowest ranking percentile  $P$  do
0:     Use Bayesian Optimization with UCB to suggest new  $\theta_i$  based on  $g(\Delta\tilde{r}; \mathcal{D})$ .
0:   end for

```

4 Experiments

4.1 Setup

We evaluate our method in two reinforcement learning environments: Cart Pole, which is a classical control environment where the agent needs to learn balancing a pole, and Lunar Lander environment, a more challenging environment where the agent needs to successfully land on a landing pad without crashing or going out of the specified bounds. We create different tasks by varying one context feature which alters the dynamics in the corresponding environment. In the Cart Pole environment, we vary the length of the pole. Agents require at least 60,000 steps in order to solve the task of balancing the pole for the entire episode without dropping it. We perturb every 5000 steps. For the Lunar Lander environment, we create two sets of variations by adjusting one context feature at a time while keeping the other fixed: Gravity and Leg height of the lander, which influence the difficulty of landing the spacecraft. Due to the complexity of this environments agents are trained for 900,000 steps, perturbing every 50,000 steps. In all experiments, we report our findings over 7 seeds. For an explanatory illustration of the environments, see figure 1.

(a) Cart Pole environment, we create different tasks by altering the length of the pole

(b) Lunar Lander environment, we create different tasks by changing the leg height and the gravitational pull

Figure 1: Comparison of Hyperparameter Schedules: PB2 vs Meta-DKL in the Lunar Lander default environment.

We use Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) as the reinforcement learning algorithm, with a population of 4 agents trained in parallel. We dynamically tune 4 hyperparameters: learning rate, clip

parameter, lambda, and number of sgd iterations. The exact search space for these hyperparameters is provided in Table 1. These hyperparameters have been shown to be important to the performance of PPO by previous work [Parker-Holder et al., 2020].

Hyperparameter	Sampling method	Bounds
Learning Rate	Log Uniform	[1e-5, 1e-3]
Clip Parameter	Uniform	[0.1, 0.5]
Lambda	Uniform	[0.9, 0.99]
Number of SGD Iterations	Uniform Integer	[3, 30]

Table 1: Hyperparameter sampling methods and bounds

4.2 Ablations

To assess the robustness of our method to varying levels of meta-data, we conduct an ablation study by varying the number of environments used for meta-data. The configurations we explore are:

- **Small:** 3 environments
- **Medium:** 5 environments
- **Large:** 10 environments

We also vary the strategy for sampling the environments used in the meta-data:

- **Equal Sampling:** We sample N environments at equal intervals from a set of 22 environments. These environments are generated by multiplying 22 values in the range $[0.1, 2.2]$ by the default value of the context feature being varied. This is motivated by creating a dataset that is as representative as possible of the entire landscape.
- **Middle Sampling:** We select the middle N environments from the set of 22 generated environments. The motivation here is that often we cannot synthesize very different environments, but rather we can create some little variation to the default configuration and it would be desirable to generalize to extreme cases.

These ablation studies allow us to evaluate the impact of the quantity and the distribution of meta-data on the performance of our approach.

5 Results

We divide our findings into subsections, each titled with a research question (RQ) that we aim to answer.

5.1 RQ1: How do Deep Kernels perform?

We display a heatmap of the median learning curves of PB2, our approach (Meta-DKL), and as an extra baseline, we add the learning curves for the default PPO agent implementation provided by Rllib [Liang et al., 2018], without any finetuning to see the gains that we can achieve with a hyperparameter schedule. For each plot, we aim to investigate how learning progresses as the agent collects more experience in the environment, so we show the number of training timesteps against the context of the environment. The intensities on the heatmap indicate how well the agent is doing in terms of reward points, where regions of darker red indicate a higher reward attained. As the agent collects more timesteps we expect it to perform better and achieve higher reward, which is indeed the general trend. We also provide a bounding box around the environments that are in distribution, meaning that their schedules were a part of the meta data fed to that experiment. As we can see, in the figures 2 and 3 clearly our meta approach outperforms PB2, in the case of varying the pole length in Cart Pole and the leg height in Lunar Lander. This is highlighted by the stronger presence of red regions in the Meta-DKL plot, for example, in figure 2 when setting the pole length to 0.7 units we see that our environment is successfully solved at 500 points by Meta-DKL, as compared to PB2, which achieves a much lower performance. We can also see in the case of lunar lander that there is a stronger

presence of red towards the lower parts of the plot which indicates that our algorithm learns faster than PB2. A very nice property is also that our meta approach shows significant gains at the 'extreme' environments, those that lie at the edges of the distribution and usually have interesting and different dynamics, compared to the default environment configuration. This is clearly visible in the case of having the agent attempt to land the lunar lander with a leg height of 1.6 units which is considered very short compared to the default environment setting of 8.0 units, and thus landing and control would be expected to be more challenging. We can clearly see that using PB2 the agent struggles and fails to achieve a mean episode reward above 0, but when using our meta-DKL approach we are able to reach a much better performance, nearing 100 reward points. Another notable observation is in the case of varying the gravity in the Y direction for the Lunar Lander environment 4. In that setup, we can see minimal improvements over PB2 in the environments that are 'in distribution'. When it comes to the environments that are further away from the distribution however we see some gains, though not as prominent as in other experiments. This possibly means that in the case of varying the gravity context feature, the task difficulty and dynamics are greatly altered and that a big portion of skills learned in one environment is not directly applicable to the other, which reflects in the hyperparameter schedules as well. This could explain why the meta data has offered minimal help and our algorithm has seemingly reverted to focusing primarily on the information signal from the task that it is currently optimizing. We also highlight that both PB2 and Meta-DKL approaches consistently outperform the default PPO configuration by a significant margin. This further highlights the strong need of hyperparameter tuning for reinforcement learning agents.

Figure 2: Heatmap of median learning curves for varying pole length in CartPole. Note how the environments at the extreme end of the shorter pole show significantly better performance

Figure 3: Heatmap of median learning curves for varying leg height in Lunar Lander.

5.2 RQ2: How does the amount of data affect performance?

We compare using different amounts of data by varying the number of meta environments that we use to draw information from. We can see that more data significantly helps in the case of varying length in Cart Pole (figure 5), as more environments perform better as we add more meta data, but the effect

Figure 4: Heatmap of median learning curves for varying gravity in Lunar Lander.

diminishes in the Lunar Lander setting (figures 6 and 7). It is however promising to see that even in our smallest setting of providing only 3 environments we see performance gains over PB2.

Figure 5: Learning heatmap comparing different dataset sizes for varying the pole length of Cart Pole

Figure 6: Learning heatmap comparing different dataset sizes for varying the leg height of Lunar Lander

5.3 RQ3: How does the distribution of data affect the performance?

We report our findings on the more challenging Lunar Lander environment. As shown in figure 8 and 9, the choice of sampling distribution can benefit environments at the extreme ends, as it provides more data from similar environments. However, this advantage may come at a slight expense to the performance in other environments that are towards the middle range. This effect can be attributed to the increased diversity of the dataset. It is also promising to see that our algorithm can generalize

Figure 7: Learning heatmap comparing different dataset sizes for varying the gravity of Lunar Lander.

even if the data provided to it is sampled from tasks with a slight variation to the default setting, as was the scenario in our previous experiments.

Figure 8: Learning heatmap comparing changing the data sampling distribution for varying the leg height of Lunar Lander

5.4 RQ4: How do the produced hyperparameter schedules compare?

An interesting finding is that our approach explores the search space in a more controlled manner. In figure 10 We display the hyperparameter schedules produced by 3 random seeds and notice that PB2 usually has aggressive transitions between the bounds of the search space, whereas Meta-DKL would transition in a more gradual manner. In order to further investigate the general search space probing trend, we plot a heatmap of the visited search space regions for 7 seeds. In order to do that we discretize our hyperparameters into bins and aggregate how many times that specific bin was visited by any of the 4 agents in that particular seed. We can see in figure 11, there are a lot of parts in the space left uncovered by PB2, in comparison to our approach.

Figure 9: Learning heatmap comparing changing the data sampling distribution for varying the gravity of Lunar Lander.

(a) Hyperparameter Schedules produced by PB2 for 3 random seeds. The scheduler tends to swing between extremes.

(b) Hyperparameter Schedules produced by Meta-DKL for 3 random seeds. We see smoother, curve-like transitions.

Figure 10: Comparison of Hyperparameter Schedules: PB2 vs Meta-DKL in the Lunar Lander default environment.

(a) PB2: Frequencies of selecting a learning rate

(b) PB2: Frequencies of selecting number of sgd iterations

Figure 11: Meta-DKL covers the search space better than PB2. We confirm that this is done in a controlled manner, where we can see smooth transitions in the hyperparameter schedules

6 Conclusion

In this work, we explored the use of meta-data from related tasks to improve the dynamic optimization of hyperparameter schedules in reinforcement learning through deep kernel Gaussian processes. Our experiments show that meta-learning can accelerate convergence, particularly when tasks are related, outpacing both static baselines and PB2.

We investigated the effect of the amount of meta-data and the choice of sampling distribution on performance. Increasing the number of meta-environments generally improved performance, with the most significant gains observed in environments like Cart Pole. In more complex tasks like Lunar Lander, however, the improvements plateaued, suggesting diminishing returns beyond a certain point. Data sampling distribution also had an impact, but did not compromise generalisation.

Our approach exhibited a unique exploration behavior, evolving hyperparameter schedules in a more controlled manner compared to PB2. This gradual approach offers valuable insights into hyperparameter tuning, suggesting it may be particularly beneficial for long-term optimization strategies.

In conclusion, incorporating meta-learning for dynamic hyperparameter scheduling enhances the reinforcement learning agent's performance, particularly in related tasks. While the benefits diminish when tasks diverge too much, our method still outperforms static configurations and offers promising directions for future research, including investigating performance gains in deep learning domains.

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